

Effectiveness of selected Gestalt Therapy Techniques on level of self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas.

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Self-esteem is a vital indicator of mental health and significantly influences academic performance, clinical competence, and overall well-being among nursing students. Low self-esteem is associated with increased stress, anxiety, and depression, particularly in demanding professional courses like nursing.

Objectives:

To assess the effectiveness of selected Gestalt therapy techniques on the level of self-esteem among nursing students and to determine the association between self-esteem and selected demographic variables.

Methods:

A quantitative experimental study with a pretest-posttest control group design was conducted among 60 nursing students selected through non-probability convenience sampling. Participants were divided into experimental and control groups. Data were collected using a demographic questionnaire and the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. The experimental group received Gestalt therapy intervention. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including paired t-test and two-sample z-test.

Results:

The mean self-esteem score in the experimental group increased significantly from 14 (pretest) to 21.9 (posttest) ($p < 0.05$). The mean change in self-esteem score was higher in the experimental group (7.9) compared to the control group (0.4), which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). No significant association was found between self-esteem and demographic variables.

Conclusion:

Gestalt therapy techniques were effective in improving self-esteem among nursing students. The findings support the inclusion of psychological interventions in nursing education to enhance students' mental health and coping abilities.

Keywords:

Self-esteem; Gestalt therapy; Nursing students; Mental health; Counseling intervention; Experimental study

INTRODUCTION

This study focuses on improving self-esteem among nursing students using Gestalt therapy techniques. Self-esteem is an important part of mental health and affects academic performance, emotional well-being, and relationships. Nursing students often face stress due to academic pressure and clinical responsibilities, which may lower their self-esteem. Therefore, this study evaluates whether Gestalt therapy can help improve their self-esteem.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Self-esteem plays a key role in emotional health, academic success, and social relationships. Nursing education is demanding and can lead to stress, burnout, and feelings of inadequacy. Studies show that students with low self-esteem often experience anxiety and depression. Gestalt therapy focuses on self-awareness and personal growth, making it useful for improving emotional well-being and self-esteem.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Nursing students experience high levels of stress, anxiety, and emotional burden during their education. Low self-esteem can negatively affect their learning, confidence, and patient care. There is a need for effective psychological interventions to support students. Gestalt therapy is a simple and practical method that may help improve self-awareness and self-esteem. Hence, this study is important to test its effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research approach using a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design to assess the effectiveness of selected Gestalt therapy techniques on self-esteem among nursing students. A total sample of 60 undergraduate nursing students was selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The sample was equally divided into an experimental group ($n = 30$) and a control group ($n = 30$). Inclusion criteria consisted of students aged 18–25 years who were willing to participate and able to understand English. Self-esteem was assessed using the standardized Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), a 4-point Likert scale. The instrument demonstrated high content validity ($CVI = 0.968$) and excellent reliability (test–retest reliability $r = 0.95$; Spearman–Brown coefficient = 0.97). The experimental group received Gestalt therapy techniques, primarily the empty chair technique, which promotes emotional expression, self-awareness, and resolution of internal conflicts. The control group did not receive any intervention during the study period. Ethical approval and institutional permission were obtained prior to data collection. Written informed consent was secured from all participants. Pre-test self-esteem scores were measured in both groups, followed by the administration of Gestalt therapy to the experimental group. Post-test assessments were conducted after the intervention. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics included mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage. Inferential statistics included paired t-test to assess within-group differences and two-sample z-test to compare changes between experimental and control groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT**Section I****Description of samples (nursing students) based on their personal characteristics****Table 4.1: Description of samples (nursing students) based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage**

n=60

Demographic variable	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Age				
19-20	0	0.0%	6	20.0%
21-22	30	100.0%	21	70.0%
23-24		0.0%	3	10.0%
Gender				
Female	19	63.3%	15	50.0%
Male	11	36.7%	15	50.0%
Course				
Basic B.Sc.	30	100.0%	30	100.0%
Type of family				
Extended Family	1	3.3%	0	0.0%
Joint family	11	36.7%	10	33.3%
Nuclear Family	17	56.7%	20	66.7%
Single parent	1	3.3%		0.0%
Family income				
Rs. 10,000- 30,000	3	10.0%	13	43.3%
Rs. 31,000- 50,000	22	73.3%	11	36.7%
Rs. 51,000- 75,000	3	10.0%	3	10.0%
Rs. 75,000- 1,00,000	2	6.7%	3	10.0%

Fig 4.1: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding age of Nursing students.

In experimental group, all the nursing students had age 21-22 years. In control group, 20% of the nursing students had age 19-20 years, 70% of them had age 21-22 years and 10% of them had age 23-24 years.

Fig 4.2: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding Gender of Nursing students.

In experimental group, 63.3% of them were females and 36.7% of them were males. In control group, 50% of them were females and 50% of them were males.

Fig 4.3: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding type of family of Nursing students.

In experimental and control group, all of them were Basic B.Sc. Nursing students. In experimental group, 3.3% of them had extended family, 36.7% of them had joint family, 56.7% of them had nuclear family and 3.3% of them had single parent family.

In control group, 33.3% of them had joint family and 66.7% of them had nuclear family.

Fig 4.4: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding family income of Nursing students.

In experimental group, 10% of them had family income Rs.10000-30000, 73.3% of them had family income Rs.30001-50000, 10% of them had family income Rs. 50001-75000 and 6.7% of them had family income Rs. 75000-100000. In control group, 43.3% of them had family income Rs.10000-30000, 36.7% of them had family income Rs.30001-50000, 10% of them had family income Rs. 50001-75000 and 10% of them had family income Rs. 75000-100000.

Section II

Analysis of data related to self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

Table 4.2: Self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=60

Self esteem	Experimental		Control	
	Pretest		Pretest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
High	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Normal	11	36.7%	11	36.7%
Low	19	63.3%	19	63.3%
Very low	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

In experimental and control group, 36.7% of them had normal self-esteem and 63.3% of them had low self-esteem.

Fig 4.5: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas in pretest.

Section III

Analysis of data related to effectiveness of Gestalt therapy on level of self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

Table 4.3: Effectiveness of Gestalt therapy on level of self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=60

Self esteem	Experimental				Control			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
High	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Normal	11	36.7%	30	100.0%	11	36.7%	12	40.0%
Low	19	63.3%	0	0.0%	19	63.3%	18	60.0%
Very low	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

In experimental and control group, in pretest, 36.7% of them had normal self-esteem and 63.3% of them had low self-esteem. In experimental group, all of them had normal self-esteem. In control group, in posttest, 40% of them had normal self-esteem and 60% of them had low self-esteem. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the self-esteem among nursing students after Gestalt therapy.

Fig 4.6: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas in pretest and post-test.

Table 4.4: Paired t-test of effectiveness of Gestalt therapy on level of self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=60

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	14.0	1.3	99.2	29	0.000
Posttest	21.9	1.4			

Research applied paired t-test of effectiveness of Gestalt therapy on level of self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas. Average self-esteem score among nursing students in experimental group in pretest 14 which increased to 21.9 in posttest. T-value for this test was 99.2 with 29 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average self esteem score in posttest was significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Gestalt therapy is significantly effective in improving the self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas.

Fig 4.7: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding Average self-esteem score among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas in pretest and post-test in experimental group.

Table 4.5: Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in self-esteem score among nursing students studying in experimental and control group

n=60

Group	Mean	SD	Z	p-value
Experimental	7.9	0.4	14.8	0.000
Control	0.4	0.5		

Research applied Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in self-esteem score among nursing students studying in experimental and control group. Average change self-esteem score among nursing students in experimental group was 7.9 which was 0.4 in control group. Z-value for this test was 14.8. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average change in self-esteem score in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Gestalt therapy is significantly effective in improving the self-esteem among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas.

Fig 4.8: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution regarding Average self-esteem score among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas in pretest and post-test in experimental group and control group.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to association between self-esteem and selected demographical variables the students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

Table 4.6: Fisher’s exact test for the association between self-esteem and selected demographical variables the students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=60

Demographic variable		Self-esteem		p-value
		Low	Normal	
Age	19-20	4	2	0.629
	21-22	33	18	
	23-24	1	2	
Gender	Female	19	15	0.190
	Male	19	7	
Type of family	Extended Family	0	1	0.761
	Joint family	13	8	
	Nuclear Family	24	13	
	Single parent	1	0	
Family income	Rs. 10,000- 30,000	11	5	0.896
	Rs. 31,000- 50,000	21	12	
	Rs. 51,000- 75,000	3	3	
	Rs. 75,000- 1,00,000	3	2	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with self-esteem among nursing students.

SUMMARY:

The results presented in this chapter show that none of the demographic variables demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with self-esteem among nursing students, as all p-values were above the 0.05 level of significance. These findings indicate that self-esteem appears to be independent of the demographic characteristics assessed in this study.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Gestalt therapy techniques on self-esteem among nursing students. Before the intervention, most students in both experimental and control groups had low self-esteem (63.3%), while only 36.7% had normal self-esteem.

After the intervention, a significant improvement was observed in the experimental group. The mean self-esteem score increased from 14 (pretest) to 21.9 (posttest). The paired t-test showed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$), indicating that Gestalt therapy was effective in improving self-esteem.

Further comparison using the two-sample z-test showed that the mean change in self-esteem score was much higher in the experimental group (7.9) compared to the control group (0.4). This difference was also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming the effectiveness of the intervention.

Additionally, no significant association was found between self-esteem and demographic variables such as age, gender, course, type of family, and family income ($p > 0.05$).

Overall, the findings suggest that Gestalt therapy techniques significantly improve self-esteem among nursing students and can be used as an effective psychological intervention.

Conclusion

The present study concludes that the selected Gestalt therapy techniques were effective in improving the level of self-esteem among students studying in nursing colleges of selected areas. The findings indicate a significant enhancement in self-esteem levels among the students who were exposed to the Gestalt therapy interventions, highlighting their usefulness in addressing emotional and psychological challenges faced by nursing students. By fostering self-awareness, personal responsibility, and acceptance of self, Gestalt therapy techniques contributed

positively to the overall psychological well-being of the participants. Therefore, the study emphasizes the importance of incorporating Gestalt therapy-based interventions into mental health promotion programs within nursing education to support students' self-esteem and holistic development

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